

Search for New Antispasmodics. Part X

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The Mannich bases (V and VI) have been obtained. The base (VI) forms the isonitroso derivative (VII), which has been reduced to the amine (VIII).

A current hypothesis (Lands and Luduena, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Therap.*, 1956, 117, 331) of antimuscarine action is that acetylcholine-sensitive receptor surfaces of parasympathetically innervated organs, can be effectively blocked by a compound which has two foci for attachment to the surface. One of these foci is a terminal tertiary or quaternary nitrogen atom and the other, which must be between 5 and 10 Å distant from the nitrogen head, may be one of a number of as yet ill-defined groupings to which is attached one or more groups large enough to constitute, like an umbrella, a protective shield over the receptors and to prevent access to them of the natural neurohormone. By considering the structure of the active antispasmodics it appears that the unshared electrons of a polarised carbonyl or ethylene group, or the lone pair on a hydroxyl oxygen, or a second nitrogen atom constitutes the second focus for attachment to the receptor surface (Goldberg and Wragg, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 4823).

An approach, based on the above hypothesis, would be to incorporate large groups in the appropriate position of a chain having two active foci, one of which is a terminal tertiary nitrogen atom; this led to the synthesis (Ghosh, Bose, and Raychaudhuri, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 319) of 4-phenyl-4-benzyl-1-piperidinobutan-3-one (I) and of 4-phenyl-4-benzyl-2-amino-1-piperidinobutan-3-one (II). These compounds, which incorporate large groups like phenyl and benzyl in the appropriate position of a chain having two active foci, have been subjected to preliminary testing in this laboratory by Dr. A. N. Bose and Shri S. Bose for antispasmodic activity. Whereas the compound (I) can neutralise the contractions due to 1 µg. of carbachol in a concentration of 10^{-6} , (II) is active even in a concentration of 10^{-8} . The compound (I) is active in neutralising histamine in a concentration of 5×10^{-6} , but (II) is active under similar conditions in a concentration of 10^{-8} . This antihistaminic activity can be attributed to the presence of an ethylamine skeleton (cf. Idson, *Chem. Rev.*, 1950, 47, 307). Both the compounds show neutralisation of barium chloride (500 µg.) stimulation of the gut at a dose level varying between 20 µg. and 100 µg. Thus these compounds show appreciable antispasmodic activity, combining both neurotropic and musculotropic action and also exerting some activity against histamine-induced spasm. The compound (II), however, lacks the requisite property of tissue binding, which is necessary for sustained action. Its *N*-acetyl derivative, on the other hand, shows an improved tissue binding while retaining the same range of activity.

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EXPERIMENTAL

1-Phenyl-2-benzylidenebutan-3-one (III: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$).—Benzaldehyde (12.8 g.) was dropwise added under stirring to a solution of benzylacetone (14.8 g.) in ethanolic hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) and the mixture was stirred for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was taken up in ether and washed free of acid. The solution was dried (sodium sulphate) and the ether removed. After a fore-run of benzylacetone and benzaldehyde, a colorless viscous liquid (10 g., b.p. 190-200°/3-4 mm) was collected. On chilling it solidified. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40-60°) in colorless needles, m.p. 72-73°. (Found: C, 86.52; H, 6.60. $C_{17}H_{16}O$ requires C, 86.44; H, 6.78%). The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 184-85°. (Found: N, 14.54. $C_{18}H_{19}ON_3$ requires N, 14.33%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethanol in red needles, m.p. 190-91°.

Palladium-charcoal (16%, 0.2 g.) was added to a solution of the above compound (III: $R = \text{Ph}$; 6 g.) in ethanol (75 c. c.) and the mixture was shaken at room temperature with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure when one equivalent of hydrogen was gradually absorbed and further absorption of hydrogen practically stopped. The solution was filtered and distilled to remove ethanol. The residue was distilled at 182-87°/10 mm to furnish a thick liquid (IV: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$; 6 g.). Vavon and Conia (*Compt. rend.*, 1946, 222, 245) reported b.p. 192-94°/15 mm. The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 153-54°. (Found: N, 14.59. $C_{18}H_{21}ON_3$ requires N, 14.24%). The oxime was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 76°. (Found: N, 5.38. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{19}ON$: N, 5.53%). Vavon and Conia (*loc. cit.*) reported m.p. 75°. The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethanol in golden needles, m.p. 123-24°. (Found: N, 13.55. Calc. for $C_{23}H_{22}O_4N_4$: N, 13.40%). Barnes and Beitchman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 5430) reported m.p. 126-27°.

1-Phenyl-2-(p-methoxy)-benzylidenebutan-3-one [III: $R_1 = C_6H_4(COCH_3(p))$] was similarly prepared by treating benzylacetone (14.8 g.) with anisaldehyde (16.3 g.) in presence of ethanolic hydrochloric acid (15 c. c.) and was obtained as a faintly coloured, thick liquid (14 g.; b.p. 230-40°/20-25 mm). On chilling it solidified and was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) in colorless plates, m.p. 79-80°. (Found: C, 80.84; H, 6.68. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 81.20; H, 6.77%). The semicarbazone was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 194°. (Found: N, 13.34. $C_{19}H_{21}O_2N_3$ requires N, 13.00%). The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from ethanol in red needles, m.p. 191°. (Found: N, 12.73. $C_{24}H_{22}O_5N_4$ requires N, 12.56%).

1-Phenyl-2-benzylidene-5-piperidinopentan-3-one (V: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$).—A mixture of (III: $R_1 = \text{Ph}$; 5.9 g.), piperidine hydrochloride (5 g.), paraformaldehyde (1.2 g.), HCl (conc., 0.15 c. c.), and ethanol (40 c. c.) was heated under reflux on the steam-bath for 12 hours. Ethanol was distilled and the residue (hydrochloride) was filtered, washed with ether, and crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 187°. (Found: C, 74.92; H, 7.74. $C_{23}H_{27}ON$, HCl requires C, 74.70; H, 7.58%). The oxalate was crystallised from ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 172°. [Found: N, 3.75. $C_{23}H_{27}ON.(CO_2H)_2$ requires N, 3.31%].

1-Phenyl-2-(p-methoxy)-benzylidene-5-piperidinopentan-3-one [V: $R_1 = C_6H_4(OCH_3(p))$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$] was similarly prepared as hydrochloride, which crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 165°. The picrate was crystallised from benzene-ethanol mixture in yellow needles, m.p. 174°. (Found: N, 9.80. $C_{24}H_{29}O_4N$. $C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires N, 9.46%).

The *oxalate* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless plates, m.p. 194-95°. [Found: N, 3.33. $C_{24}H_{29}O_2N.(CO_2H)_2$ requires N, 3.09%].

1-*Phenyl-2-benzyl-5-piperidinopentan-3-one* (VI: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$). — Palladium-charcoal (10%; 0.2 g.) was added to a solution of the hydrochloride of (V: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$; 6 g.) in ethanol (175 c.c.) and the mixture was shaken at room temperature with hydrogen at atmospheric pressure when one equivalent of hydrogen was gradually absorbed and further absorption of hydrogen practically stopped. The catalyst was removed by filtration and washed with ethanol. The filtrate and washings were combined and removal of ethanol left a viscous liquid which was purified by acid-ammonia treatment. The *hydrochloride* was prepared and was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 154°. (Found: C, 74.48; H, 7.62. $C_{23}H_{29}ON.HCl$ requires C, 74.29; H, 8.07%). The *oxalate* was crystallised from ethanol in colorless rectangular plates, m.p. 145-46°. [Found: N, 3.42. $C_{23}H_{29}ON.(CO_2H)_2$ requires N, 3.29%].

The above hydrochloride was obtained when (IV: $R_1 = Ph$) was allowed to react with piperidine hydrochloride and paraformaldehyde in the usual way.

1-*Phenyl-2-benzyl-4-oximino-5-piperidinopentan-3-one* (VII: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$). — Butylⁿ nitrite (3 g.) was added to a cooled suspension of hydrochloride of (VI: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$; 3.6 g.) in anhydrous ether (40 c. c.). Dry hydrochloric acid gas was passed till saturation, when a deep red-coloured solution was obtained. After keeping overnight in the cold, the mixture was poured in ice and the solution was shaken with ether. The aqueous solution was basified with ammonia when a solid (2.5 g.) was obtained. It was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 100-101°. (Found: N, 7.99. $C_{23}H_{28}O_2N_2$ requires N, 7.69%).

1-*Phenyl-2-benzyl-4-amino-5-piperidinopentan-3-one* (VIII: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$). — Palladium-charcoal (10%; 0.1 g.) was added to a solution of (VII: $R_1 = Ph$; $R_2 = \text{piperidino}$; 2.5 g.) in ethanol (200 c. c.) and the mixture was shaken at room temperature in an atmosphere of hydrogen. When an equivalent quantity of hydrogen was absorbed, the catalyst was filtered and the filtrate was made acidic to Congo red by passing dry hydrochloric acid gas. The solvent was then removed and the residue was crystallised from ethanol-ether mixture in colorless needles, m.p. 160-62°. (Found: C, 71.78; H, 8.41; N, 7.55. $C_{23}H_{30}ON_2.HCl$ requires C, 71.41; H, 8.02; N, 7.24%).

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